
MARKETING STRATEGIES TO REACH BUSINESSES IN DISADVANTAGED AREAS: AN EFFICIENT APPROACH.

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Introduction:

Companies operating in disadvantaged areas often face unique challenges in terms of marketing and expanding their business. These regions may have poor infrastructure, limited access to financial resources, and a restricted local market. However, with marketing strategies that are appropriate and adapted to local conditions, it is possible to overcome these barriers and achieve business success. In this article, we will discuss some effective strategies to help businesses expand their presence in disadvantaged areas.

Keywords: Digital marketing, business, precarious.

Abstract

Companies operating in disadvantaged areas often face unique challenges in terms of marketing and expanding their business. These regions may have poor infrastructure, limited access to financial resources, and a restricted local market. However, with proper marketing strategies that are tailored to local conditions, it is possible to overcome these barriers and achieve business success. In this article, we will discuss some effective strategies to help businesses expand their presence in underserved areas.

1. Understanding the Local Market:

Before implementing any marketing strategy, it is critical to conduct detailed research of the local market. This involves understanding the needs and preferences of local consumers, identifying regional competitors, and taking an indepth look at the regulatory and economic environment in the area. This information provides a solid foundation for developing effective marketing strategies that are tailored to the specific conditions of the disadvantaged region.

2. Personalization of Marketing Messages:

A successful marketing approach in disadvantaged areas involves tailoring the messages to meet the needs and interests of the local audience. This can include developing products or services that are tailored to the demands of the community, as well as creating advertising campaigns that resonate with the local culture and values.

Personalization demonstrates a genuine commitment to the community and helps build strong relationships with customers.

3. Establishing Local Partnerships:

Partnerships with local organizations, such as NGOs, trade associations, and educational institutions, can be an effective strategy for expanding the company's presence in disadvantaged areas. These partnerships offer access to established networks in the community, additional resources,

and valuable insights into local needs. In addition, local collaborations demonstrate a tangible commitment to the sustainable development of the region.

4. Use of Technology:

Technology plays a crucial role in overcoming challenges in disadvantaged areas. Digital marketing strategies such as content marketing, social media, and online advertising can be particularly effective in reaching a wider audience in a cost-effective manner. The use of e-commerce platforms can also help businesses expand their presence beyond the geographical limitations of the region.

5. Active Community Involvement:

Community engagement is essential to establishing a lasting presence in disadvantaged areas. This goes beyond simply offering products or services and involves supporting local initiatives, events, and social causes. Establishing a positive reputation in the community not only increases public trust but also strengthens the bonds between the business and its local customers.

Companies that are able to reach wider audiences in geographical terms, from all cultures, are able to increase their number of customers, and for this to happen, it is necessary to bring access to technology to all peoples (KOTLER ET AL, 2017). Regarding the market created with the growth of the internet, Cintra (2010) reveals that people who buy products or services over the internet are directly influenced by objective information. This information is provided through the detailing of the characteristics of the product/service or by the opinions of other people.

Conclusion:

While reaching businesses in disadvantaged areas presents unique challenges, tailored and well-executed marketing strategies can

overcome these barriers and lead to business success. By understanding the local market, personalizing marketing messages, establishing local partnerships, utilizing technology effectively, and actively engaging in the community, businesses can not only expand their presence in these regions but also contribute to the sustainable development of disadvantaged communities. Not only does this approach benefit businesses, but it also creates a significant positive impact on local communities.

KOTLER, Philip; KELLER, Kevin Lane. Marketing administration.

Translation: Sonia Midori Yamamoto. Technical review by Edson Crescitelli.

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¹Jeane Souza de Paula is a highly qualified professional with extensive experience in areas such as sales, marketing, commercial and strategic planning. Graduated in Business Administration from Universidade Veiga de Almeida (UVA) in 2011, she also has a technical degree in Accounting from Escola Estadual Central do Brasil, completed in 1997. Her dedication to professional improvement is evident in her certification in Small Business Administration, earned in 2020.

With a professional career of more than 10 years, Jeane has accumulated experience in several sectors, including health plans, insurance, pharmacy and automotive. His comprehensive knowledge and skill in a variety of areas have been instrumental in driving the growth and success of the companies he has worked for.

²Nayara Cordeiro Rodrigues de Souza is a prominent professional in the area of Human Resources, with more than 15 years of experience. With a degree in Human Resources from Estácio in São Paulo, she stood out for her ability in strategic HR management in several companies. With expertise in recruitment, talent development, and benefits administration, Mayara is recognized for her inspiring leadership and effective communication. Today, she continues her successful trajectory

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³Juliana Silva is a highly qualified professional with over a decade of experience in the financial industry. With a degree in Financial Management Technology from UNINOVE and certified by ANBID CPA-10, Juliana has excelled in positions such as Teller and Personal Account Manager at Banco Bradesco S.A. Her expertise in financial analysis and exceptional customer service skills make her a valued figure in her field. With an ongoing commitment to professional excellence, Juliana continues to reach new heights of success in her glittering career.

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